

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF ORGANIZING UPBRINGING LESSONS IN COMMON SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article reflects the pedagogical and psychological conditions of organizing education classes in primary classes. Innovative educational technologies and interactive educational methods used in educational classes are described.*

Keywords: *innovative education, interactive educational methods, competence approach, professional competence, modern educational technologies.*

Pedagogical possibilities of developing professional competences of future elementary school teachers based on innovative educational technologies, pedagogical and psychological conditions of organizing educational classes in the educational environment, we can see in this article.

Innovative, interactive education allows future elementary school teachers to constantly creative search, continuous development and improvement of their personality. Educational activities carried out in higher education institutions should be focused on the personality of future primary school teachers, their interest, desire, desire, and need, that is, it is required to focus on individualization of education. . Now what should be understood by individualization of education? let's answer the question. Therefore, the quality and efficiency of education is related to the effective engagement of future elementary school teachers with independent reading aimed at mastering the content of education, independent thinking and thinking activities.

When conducting the lesson process on the basis of interactive methods, it is possible to see the development of the following characteristics in the future elementary school teachers: The student is not only taught, but also taught to study, learn, work, master independently. Students are taught to learn through independent analysis, to think creatively, to think freely based on personal conclusions. The skills of being able to think against thoughts alien to us, to defend one's point of view are formed. Future elementary school teachers will be given the opportunity to creatively observe by searching, finding, and processing knowledge from textbooks, information-resource centers, the Internet, and various other sources, without ready-made knowledge. Future elementary school teachers are taught to work with *textbooks*, read, study, write a synopsis, use additional literature and resources to acquire independent learning skills.

All students in the audience are guaranteed to master their abilities. The student's mastery and ability to use the acquired knowledge in everyday life and practical activities is determined by the level of skills and qualifications. If the professor-teacher learns to work with students on the basis of interactive methods and can bring it into their educational activities, all students will achieve almost the same results.

When the teaching process is organized on the basis of interactive methods:

- mutual activity of students increases, cooperation and co-creative skills are formed.

- the skills of working with the curriculum, program, educational content, textbook, standard, norm, manuals are formed.

- independent reading, working, mastering of the educational content and text becomes daily personal work.

- the student gets used to freely expressing his opinion, defending his opinion, being able to prove and confirm it.

- most importantly, didactic motives arise during the educational process. That is, the student's desire, desire and desire are satisfied, and because the lesson is interesting, he does not know that time is passing. The student's personal interest increases in the learning process. This situation raises future elementary school teachers to a higher level in their pursuit and achievement of educational goals.

Advantages of organizing lessons in interactive methods.

- leads to good mastering of teaching content.

- educational relations are established between student - professor-teacher - students in due time.

Teaching methods take different forms during the educational process (individual, pair, group, large group). The learning process becomes highly motivated by satisfying the need for learning. Educational material is better remembered by mutual information giving, receiving, and processing. During the learning process, the student's self-evaluation and critical view develop. For the student, the lesson becomes an interesting content of the taught subject. A creative approach to the study process, a positive attitude is manifested. It leads to the ability of each student to think independently, to search, to observe. In interactive lessons, the student not only learns the educational content, but also develops his critical and logical thinking. When organizing a lesson in interactive methods, the development of a student's personality should begin with creating a foundation for himself. That is, the student:

learn by reading and studying independently;

self-realization, self-education;

to look confidently at one's strength and capabilities;

to look at educational work with a sense of responsibility;

to be able to organize their activities independently, to enjoy every minute;

to be able to arouse desire for educational work;

to be able to show activity in any situation;

in particular, it is necessary to learn to make effective use of current information sources as the main and main goal.

What is the purpose of using non-traditional teaching methods? What are its advantages and the principles of improving the effectiveness of the lesson? the question can be answered based on the following results.

1. Non-traditional teaching is the simplest and most convenient method.

2. Teaches independent thinking.

3. Multidisciplinary.

4. Simple and easy.

5. Increases wealth of knowledge.

6. Wins time.

7. It will be fun.

8. Increases the effectiveness of the lesson.
9. Expands worldview.
10. Develops thinking.
11. Attracts students' attention.
12. Treats each student individually.
13. Strengthens memory.
14. Invites to search.
15. Encourages students to work on themselves.

The goal of training is to impart knowledge and skills to future elementary school teachers in the state educational standards. Teaching can be considered successful only when the knowledge is received and understood by the student, or the student can demonstrate in practice the tasks intended for skill development.

Organization on the basis of interactive methods of teaching subjects in the preparation of future primary school teachers for professional activities - effective use of innovative technologies in the organization of educational work organized in them, as well as future primary school it is a process of pedagogical activity aimed at achieving efficiency in imparting knowledge to teachers and educating them, in which a number of pedagogical tasks must be solved. They consist of:

- Creating certain conditions for the organization of lesson processes in higher education institutions based on interactive methods;
- Organization of special educational seminars aimed at revealing the essence of interactive methods among professors and teachers of higher education institutions;
- to achieve thorough assimilation of the basics of innovative technology by them;
- Cultivating a sense of creative approach to the organization of educational activities among professors and teachers of higher education institutions;
- Formation of organizational skills and competencies in professors and teachers of higher education institutions based on innovative technological approach;
- Achieving the organization of educational work by professors of higher education institutions based on interactive methods;
- Improving the skills of professors and teachers of higher education institutions in organizing pedagogical activities based on innovative technology;
- Ensuring the effectiveness of the teaching process in higher education institutions.

The formation of the competence of future primary school teachers to organize pedagogical activities based on interactive methods is achieved on the basis of the following principles:

1. The determination of the single goal of organizing training in primary education in higher education institutions based on interactive methods.
2. Consistent, purposeful, systematic and continuous implementation of activities on the basis of interactive methods in primary education.
3. Taking into account the existing conditions and subjective approaches in the organization of classes conducted in primary education on the basis of interactive methods.
4. Free demonstration of pedagogical skills and talents.
5. Promotion of new experiences.
6. Unit of theoretical and practical activity.
7. Cooperation with donor organizations of foreign countries, etc., in the organization of trainings in primary education based on interactive methods.

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